

BUCKLING OF COMPOSITE PLATES MADE OF REPEATED SUBLAMINATE CONSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

Buckling is one of the important failure modes of composite plates. Repeated sublaminate construction of composite plates is employed in industry to reduce manufacturing errors and also to produce more damage tolerant laminates. In this type of construction, basic sublaminate has a small number of plies, for example, 8, 6, or 4 and the full laminate is obtained by repeating the basic sublaminate. The work presented in this paper deals with optimising the orientations of the plies in each sublaminate so as to achieve maximum buckling load for the given laminate thickness. Axial compression, Shear and combined loading are considered. First, knowing the sublaminate stiffnesses the overall laminate stiffness is obtained using parallel axis theorem. All possibilities of stacking the sublaminates are considered. Using orthotropic plate theory buckling loads are obtained. Subsequently ranking is done based on load carrying ability before buckling. It is found that very significant increase in buckling loads can be had by proper choice of orientations of plies within the sublaminate. Quasi-isotropic laminates are, in most cases, far from the optimum.

INTRODUCTION

Buckling is an important mode of failure of structural components. Composites are extensively used in aerospace industry. In aerospace engineering, the aim is to realise the full potential of composite materials and reduce the weight of a structure. Many a time, composite laminates are made using repeated sublaminate construction. In this type of construction, basic sublaminate has a small number of plies, for example, 8, 6 or 4 and the full laminate is obtained by repeating the basic sublaminate. The advantages of such construction are: i) Easier selection of optimum ply angles ii) a more damage tolerant laminate resulting from maximum splicing or mixing of plies and iii) simpler lay up resulting in lower cost and fewer errors in production.

The work presented in this paper deals with optimising the orientations of the plies in each sublaminate so as to achieve maximum buckling load for the given laminate thickness. The given panel is idealised as a homogeneous orthotropic plate whose stiffness properties are determined based on the sublaminate (which is repeated) stiffness. Critical buckling loads are obtained using conventional orthotropic plate theory derived on the basis of Kirchhoff-Love assumptions. Checks are made to ensure correctness of the computer program developed, by comparing with available solutions of isotropic and orthotropic plates. Next application is made to a large class of T300/N5208 [0,90,45,-45] plates with Quadri-directional, tri-directional and bi-directional lay-up schemes and the results are merit listed from buckling point of view. Such ranking of the lamination schemes based on critical buckling

loads, does not only help in the choice of the optimum lamination scheme but also help in assessing any ply drop scheme.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS AND PROCEDURE USED

The equation governing the buckling behaviour of an orthotropic plate is ²

$$D_{11} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + D_{22} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} - N_x \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} - 2N_{xy} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} - N_y \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} = 0$$

where D_{11} , D_{12} , D_{22} and D_{66} are the plate flexural stiffnesses and N_x , N_y and N_{xy} are the inplane stress resultant components and w is the deflection normal to the x - y plane.

The potential energy U is ²

$$U = 1/2 \int_0^a \int_0^b \left\{ D_{11} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + 2D_{12} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \right) + 4D_{66} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 + D_{22} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 + N_x \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 + 2N_{xy} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right) + N_y \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right\} dx dy$$

First the flexural stiffnesses D_{11} , D_{12} , D_{22} , D_{66} (1,2 refer to the laminate axes) of the homogeneous orthotropic plate which is nearly equivalent to the given composite panel is obtained knowing the sublaminates stiffnesses and using parallel axis theorem. Only symmetric laminates are considered (Fig. 1). Then we use conventional methods, either differential equation based³ or energy based⁴, to predict the buckling loads. The design process consists of two steps: i) determine first the optimum ply angles in the sublaminates and ii) find the required number of sublaminates.

FIG.1. REPEATED SUBLAMINATE CONSTRUCTION

LAMINATE STIFFNESSES

Let the stiffness matrices of the sublaminates (Fig.1) be $[A^0]$, $[B^0]$ and $[D^0]$. Then the stiffness matrices of the total laminate are

$$\begin{cases} [A] = 2r[A^0] \\ [B] = 0 \\ [D] = 2r\{[D^0] + (r-1)u[B^0] + (r-1)(2r-1)u^2[A^0]/6\} \end{cases}$$

where $2r$ is the total number of sublaminates
 u is the thickness of the sublaminate

LAMINATE RANKING

We consider the families of the following $\pi/4$ sublaminates¹.

- 35, 8-ply, Quadri-directional sublaminates starting with the code [5111], [4211],.....[1115]
- 40, 6-ply, tridirectional sublaminates starting with the code [4110], [3210],.....[0114]
- 18, 4-ply, bidirectional sublaminates starting with the code [3100], [2200],.....[0013]
- 6, 2-ply, bidirectional sublaminates starting with the code [1100], [0011].

where sublaminate code designates the number ofplies in the order of 0, 90, 45, -45 degrees. Thus [5111] designates[0₅/90/45/-45].

There are a total of 99 sublaminates among the four families above. Buckling being a phenomenon primarily governed by bending and twisting stiffnesses, the location of a ply with respect to the middle plane of the laminate is very important. So, we consider each one of the 99 sublaminates and consider all possibilities of stacking. For example, in the case of the sublaminate $[N_1, N_2, N_3, N_4]$, there are 24 combinations possible such as $[N_1, N_2, N_3, N_4], [N_1, N_2, N_4, N_3], [N_1, N_3, N_2, N_4], \dots$ etc. Therefore, we have for the family of

- * 35, 8-ply sublaminates, 840 combinations
- * 40, 6-ply sublaminates, 240 combinations
- * 18, 4-ply sublaminates, 36 combinations and
- * 6, 2-ply sublaminates, 12 combinations

Thus in all, corresponding to the 99 sublaminate schemes we have 1128 combinations to be considered for buckling analysis. We introduce the following new notation to define these laminates.

- Integer 1 - denotes 0^o ply
- Integer 2 - denotes 90^o ply
- Integer 3 - denotes 45^o ply
- Integer 4 - denotes -45^o ply

For example an 8 ply sublaminate can be [1111234] or [23111114] etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A computer program has been developed to compute the buckling loads and rank the sublaminate schemes based on buckling loads. Checks are made^{5,6,7} for various cases to ensure the correctness of the program by comparing with available solution of isotropic and orthotropic plates. For presenting numerical results we choose T300/N5208 system with the following ply properties

$$\begin{aligned} E_L &= 181.0 \text{ GPa} ; E_T = 10.3 \text{ GPa} ; G_{LT} = 7.17 \text{ GPa} \\ \nu_{LT} &= 0.28 ; \text{ Ply thickness} = 0.125 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

EFFECT OF NUMBER OF SUBLAMINATES (NSUB)

Fig.2 shows typically the effect of NSUB on $(D_{11})_{\min}/(D_{11})_{\max}$ where $(D_{11})_{\min}$ and $(D_{11})_{\max}$ represent the lowest and highest values of D_{11} corresponding to the 24 combinations that are possible for $[N_1, N_2, N_3, N_4]$ ($N_1=2, N_2=2, N_3=2, N_4=2$) (ie. the Quasi-isotropic case). It is seen that when NSUB is small, the variation in D_{11}

is large and as NSUB becomes larger, variation in D_{11} reduces. At 16 repeats the maximum percentage variation is about 15%. Similar computations were performed for D_{22} , D_{66} and D_{12} . The typical variation as can be seen from Table 1 in all cases is very similar to Fig.2. Thus, it is necessary to consider all possibilities of lay-up schemes (840 for the 8 ply case) in order to obtain the optimum lay-up scheme.

Fig.2. Effect of number of sublaminae on D_{11}

Table 1. Effect of NSUB on laminate Stiffnesses
Lay-up $[N_1, N_2, N_3, N_4]$ ($N_1=5, N_2=1, N_3=1, N_4=1$)

NSUB	2	4	6	8	12	16
$\frac{(D_{11})_{\min}}{(D_{11})_{\max}}$	0.4126	0.6636	0.7630	0.8187	0.8743	0.9050
$\frac{(D_{22})_{\min}}{(D_{22})_{\max}}$	0.1500	0.4181	0.5647	0.6502	0.7536	0.8071
$\frac{(D_{12})_{\min}}{(D_{12})_{\max}}$	0.217	0.4869	0.6215	0.6998	0.7893	0.8375
$\frac{(D_{66})_{\min}}{(D_{66})_{\max}}$	0.2593	0.5173	0.6591	0.7220	0.8051	0.8510

APPLICATIONS

First we consider the example of a square plate 0.25m x 0.25m of NSUB=4 with all edges simply supported and subjected to uniaxial compression. Table 2 shows the 1128 sublaminates ranked based on buckling loads. We see that [12333444] gives a critical load which is 24% higher than [44332211] corresponding to a Quasi-isotropic case. Also [12333444] gives a buckling load which is higher by 41% compared to that of [14322222]. It is clear that Quasi-isotropic case is far from the optimum. In many aerospace structures (for example aircraft wing skin) plies are dropped in zones of lower loads. Tables like the one presented here will help to assess any ply drop scheme from buckling point of view.

The optimum lay-up scheme for NSUB=4 for the 8,6,4 and 2 ply cases corresponding to various loading and boundary conditions are presented in Table 3 and 4.

Table 2. Ranking of 8, 6, 4, and 2 ply schemes based on buckling of a 0.25m x 0.25m, Simply Supported Panel (Uniaxial Compression)

No. of Plies	Sl. No.	Code	P _{crit} MN/m	No. of Plies	Sl. No.	Code	P _{crit} MN/m
8	1	12333444	0.307587	4	1	3334	0.0404586
	2	12444333	0.307587		2	4333	0.0404586
	3	12334444	0.307587		3	3344	0.0404586
	840	14322222	0.181402		36	4222	0.0177478
6	1	233344	0.132398	2	1	34	0.00505733
	2	244333	0.132398		2	43	0.00505733
	3	133444	0.132398		3	13	0.00440884
	240	432222	0.067506		12	21	0.00298216

Table 3. Optimum lay-up schemes for buckling of the 0.25m x 0.25m panel for various boundary conditions

a = 8 plies; b = 6 plies; c = 4 plies; d = 2 plies

Loading		Optimum Lay-up Schemes				
		SSSS	CCCC	CSCS	SCSC	CCSS
Uniaxial Compression	a	12333444	22444133	23411111	23333144	12344444
	b	233344	111334	341111	314444	233344
	c	3334	3311	3111	1444	3334
	d	34	43	41	34	34

Table.4. Optimum lay-up scheme for buckling of the 0.25mx0.25m panel for various loading conditions
a = 8 plies; b = 6 plies; c = 4 plies; d = 2 plies

Optimum Lay-up Schemes					
Boundary condition	$N_y = 100000.0$		$N_x = 1000.0$		
	$N_{xy} = \Delta$	$N_x = \Delta$	$N_{xy} = \Delta$	$N_x = \Delta$	
	N/m	N/m	N/m	$\beta = 0.25$ N/m	
SSSS	a	13332224	12333444	13332224	12333444
	b	222234	333314	322244	133334
	c	4442	3111	4442	3334
	d	23	41	23	34

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The work presented in this paper pertains to elastic buckling of rectangular composite laminates made of repeated sublaminates construction. A large class of [0,90,45,-45] lamination schemes are examined. Significant gain can be had by proper choice of the lay up scheme compared to Quasi-isotropic case. Based on these lines an expert system could be developed for design of composite laminates for buckling. Currently, work is under progress in this direction.

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